

The growth of flora in Isla Verde and its flora diversity from various landscapes

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Abstract

Plant biodiversity is such a crucial part in any ecosystem because it helps prevent the extinction of species for they serve as a habitat and its presence allows other organisms to adapt and change in the environment. One of the reasons why population scientists keep track of the plant population is because the appropriate plant population or density for any specific situation produces mature plants that are dense enough to use resources like water, nutrients, and sunlight effectively, but not so dense that some plants die or even become unproductive (Lyon, 2009; Kavut et al., 2014). The researchers gathered specimens from Isla Verde, specifically at Mt. Dagitdagit using the quadrat and random sampling method. The researchers took branches from plants and stored them into polyethylene bags for coding and denaturation. The denatured plants were then pressed and identified; the pressed plants are attached to an A3 sized vellum board for classification and further analysis. The plants are listed into an illustrated table that identifies if the plants are present in each quadrat or not, so that the researchers can identify the factors that lie within the flora that are situated in the same coordinates but differs in landscape. Twenty (20) plants that were gathered in total showed the premise of the growth of flora in Isla Verde and its flora diversity from various landscapes because one of the plants that were present in both quadrats possesses a quality from a family of plants that no other plant from two quadrats had.

Keywords: *Flora; Flora diversity; Growth; Isla Verde; Landscapes.*

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Introduction

Isla Verde is an island that connects the islands of Mindoro and Luzon in the Verde Island Passage (VIP). It is a land mass barely affected by man caused by deforestation and landscape deformation (Dulce, 2015). It rises in the middle of the Verde Island Passage, which is known for its abundant marine species and is referred to as "the center of the center" of marine biodiversity everywhere. The Verde Island Passage serves as a biodiversity reservoir to rehabilitate depleted reefs in the Coral Triangle and the Philippines. The Coral Triangle Region, which is surrounded by the six nations: the Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Timor Leste, and the Solomon Islands, is a hotspot of marine biodiversity on the planet (De Vera-Ruiz, 2018; Gonzales & Gosliner, 2014). Other than the island being well-renowned for its stupendous marine biodiversity, it also has its own tropical rainforests (Godoy, 2019).

Isla Verde's rainforests go all the way to the island's mountain Mt. Dagitdagit, ranging up to 250 m to 300 m tall (820 ft to 1000 ft) and a land area of 1625.05 hectares wide (Devitt & Tirona, 2015). The island is inhabited by typical citizens and some indigenous folks; it has a total of six (6) barangays and two

(2) tribes. The island is being provided with electrical power through solar panels and generators (Guerrero, 2018).

Two-thirds of Earth's biodiversity and between 70% and 80% of all plant and animal species are found in the Philippines, one of the world's 18 mega biodiverse countries. The Philippines maintains 5% of the world's flora and ranks fifth in terms of plant species. There are 800 different species of orchids, 1,000 different ferns, and 8,000 different blooming plant species among the rich flora. However, it is projected that between 2000 and 2005, the Philippines lost 2.1% of its forest cover yearly, ranking seventh in the world and having the second-fastest rate of deforestation in Southeast Asia (behind Myanmar) (Convention on Biological Diversity, n.d.). On the other hand, the mesophytic deep reefs need strong protection because there is recorded evidence of human impacts at the twilight zone, 200 to 500 feet below the ocean's surface (Rocha et al., 2017). In this research, the primary objective is to determine the flora diversity in Mt. Dagitdagit.

Methodology

The researchers aimed to perform a quadrat sampling procedure so that the gathered specimens from the peak and foot of the mountain of Mt. Dagitdagit can be identified, recorded, and analyzed as to how much of the biodiversity of the flora from the peak of the mountain is present in the lower levels of the mountain.

The researchers travelled to Isla Verde located at the coordinates N 13d 33m 53s, E121d 03m 04s where they can trek the mountains of Mt. Dagitdagit and take plant specimens. The researchers gathered branches of situated plants in a chosen area of 10m X 10m quadrat. The researchers mostly picked some parts of the plants that consist of reproductive parts such as flowers and fruits and put them in each of the polyethylene bags, photographed, and coded for identification. When the researchers arrived back on camp, all the gathered, coded, and photographed branches were inserted into a trash bag and were immersed with denaturing alcohol. The plants were then pressed into a plant presser after being drained and dried out of their immersion to the denaturing alcohol. The pressed plants were affixed into an A3 sized vellum boards and were identified respectively by the researchers.

The researchers used random and quadrat samplings; wherein to draw conclusions about a population, a random sample of observations from that population is chosen. A traditional method for studying ecology, particularly biodiversity, is quadrat sampling. This means that a set number of squares (called quadrats) are placed, and the species found within each quadrat are recognized and recorded.

Results and Discussion

The purpose of the discussion is to interpret and describe the significance of the findings regarding the identified plants from different quadrats. The researchers listed each of the gathered and identified plants in an illustrated table seen below.

Table 1. Plant specimens from different quadrats

Plant Specimens	Q1	Q2
<i>Pleurothyrium trianae</i>	/	
<i>Micromelum compressum</i>	/	/
<i>Bridelia micrantha</i>	/	
<i>Tabernaemontana pandacaqui</i>	/	
<i>Chromolaena odorata</i>	/	
<i>Vismia guianensis</i>	/	
<i>Leucaena leucocephala</i>		/
<i>Delonix regia</i>		/
<i>Pterospermum heterophyllum</i>		/
<i>Trillium undulatum</i>		/
Species 1		/
<i>Garcinia corsa</i>	/	
<i>Ardisia humilis</i>	/	
Species 2	/	
<i>Ficus septica</i>	/	
<i>Heliopsis helianthoides</i>		/
<i>Laurus nobilis</i>	/	
<i>Citrus aurantiifolia</i>	/	
<i>Lansium parasiticum</i>	/	

Growth of Different Flora from Various Terrain

The researchers gathered a total of 20 plants from both quadrats. There are 13 plants gathered from the first quadrat and seven (7) from the second quadrat, but there are 19 plant species in total because *Micromelum compressum* is present in both quadrats. The plants that are found within the first quadrat appear to be almost prominently absent within the second quadrat which is situated along the trails and by the foot of the mountain. The data presents that the plants gathered from the first quadrat that is situated in the mountains peak is isolated enough to possess different species of wooden trees compared to the shrubs that can be found thousands of feet below the elevated landscape. The only plant that is present from both quadrats within the island is no other than that of the *Micromelum compressum*, which is part of the genus of the subtribe Micromelinae, technically known as the very remote citroid fruit trees (Siebert Wooldridge, 2016).

This proves that Isla Verde possesses an unusually rich flora that varies its plant species depending on the location which is similarly enough to the islands of Samos in which it says that there are elements favoring the diverse plant growth that come together with striking effect on Samos. Its islands have plenty of high grounds and the proximity of the Turkish mountains ensure a good winter rainfall. Limestone geology, too, supports a wide range of plants (Anderson, 1994). Given that most of the plants gathered by the researchers are evergreen shrubs from the bottom of the trees from the top, it does not shy from the fact that plant growth and abundance of flora is affected by different elements of a terrain such as island mountain, rock formation, and positioning of habitat for animals to thrive on.

One of the other possible factors for their presence in certain locations of the island shows that they can thrive in locations that favor their growth or else they would not be growing there in the first place considering their ability to disperse seeds and reproduce to different locations or perhaps their inability to do so for not being found in one of both places. Some factors such as vertical seed dispersal, such that the movement of seeds upward or downward is thought to be an essential part in a plant's ability to survive climate change or reproductive succession (Naoy et al., 2019). The survival and growth of seedlings were also affected by the generally weaker growth conditions on the upper plateau, which included less soil of lower quality and a drier habitat (Hansen et al., 2008).

Conclusion

The plants from the first and second quadrats provided tangible data that we can observe and distinguish which plants are present or absent from different quadrats that are situated from different terrestrial locations within the same island; it is evident that the plants that were gathered seem to have a correlation but have no possible causation as to how a citrus plant such as *Micromelum compressum* managed to attain a prominent presence in both quadrats. The researchers have drawn their conclusion which pertains to the notion that the Verde Island of Batangas contains an unusual biodiversity of flora and its flora from the peak of Mt. Dagitdagit down to its floors are well-diverse in terms of plant life and ecosystems.

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